

Bacteria-diamond-metal nanoparticle complexes for life science applications: AFM-in-SEM analysis and methodology

To elucidate the interaction mechanisms and effects at the interface between microorganisms and nanomaterials requires multi-faceted microscopic methods. *In-situ* synthesis of plasmonic nanoparticles on chitosan-coated hydrogenated nanodiamonds offers enhanced stability and allows for studying nanomaterial interactions with negatively charged *E.coli* bacteria by novel methodology combining AFM and SEM.

Figure 1: Schematic drawing of electrostatic colloidal assembly of bacteria-metal-diamond complexes, the concept of simultaneous acquisition of electronic and topographical information from such multicomponent sample on a registration grid, and scanning electron microscopy imaging showing a view of AFM cantilever navigation to bacteria clusters with nanoparticle complexes.

Positively-charged nanocomposites interact with negatively-charged bacteria in a liquid environment before addition to carbon-coated alphanumerical grids for correlative analysis. Regions of interest are located and the grid reference recorded to improve the efficiency of further analysis. Microscopic topographical information (AFM) is acquired simultaneously with chemical, material, and morphological information (SEM) from the same bacteria-diamond-metal nanoparticle complex analyzed under identical measurement conditions.

The uncoated bacteria-diamond-metal nanoparticle sample enables different information to be revealed depending on the SEM operating parameters (SE and BSE detectors at varied acceleration voltages). By first creating three separate SEM images, a colorized composite image can be created from the same region of interest to identify each component of the sample. Finally, an overlay with the topographical information (AFM) creates a **3-D RGB correlative probe-electron microscopy (CPEM) image**.

Topography of the complex formed by bacteria-diamond-metal nanoparticle interactions in combination with the variation in color-coded SEM images reveals different arrangement and locations of the diamond-metal nanocomposite relative to the bacteria. Only through this correlative analytical approach it was possible to reveal the precise location of the enhanced interaction between the bacteria and the stabilized plasmonic nanoparticles. This technique of preparing a 3-D color-coded image can be used to better visualize many other types of nanomaterial interactions in life science samples.

3-D RGB image from AFM & SEM

Figure 2: Workflow procedure and the result of creation of a colorized 3-D RGB image from AFM & SEM data obtained simultaneously on the life science sample at the same region of interest and under the same conditions.

